

Studies in Zirconium Oxide Sols. Part I. Electrical Conductance of Zirconium Oxide Sols

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Concentrated zirconium oxide sols of fairly high degree of purity have been prepared by hydrolysing zirconium nitrate, followed by continued hot dialysis. When diluted sols are allowed to age, the specific conductance increases due to desorption of the adsorbed electrolyte. In the case of the concentrated sol, ageing results in the decrease of specific conductance due to aggregation of the particles. Equivalent conductance of the micelles on dilution first decreases and then increases on further dilution, showing the behaviour of a typical colloidal electrolyte.

Trivedi, Divatia, and Patani (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, **36A**, 530 et seq.) pointed out that the equivalent conductance of the micelles in a colloidal system decreased on dilution and then increased on further dilution, the latter being the normal behaviour of an electrolyte. In the present investigation, conductance of zirconium oxide sol has been studied and it has been concluded that the curve of equivalent conductance against the square root of concentration passes through a minimum; this behaviour is more marked when the purity of the sol is increased. Zirconium oxide sol was previously studied by Sharma and Dhar (this *Journal*, 1932, **9**, 455), who observed an increase in conductance on ageing. This has been confirmed in the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Several methods may be employed to prepare zirconium oxide sols (Blitz, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 4431; Ruer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, **43**, 282; Sharma and Dhar, *loc. cit.*). In the present investigation, the sol was prepared by hydrolysis of zirconium nitrate, following the method of Sharma and Dhar (*loc. cit.*). The sol so obtained was subjected to continued hot dialysis (Neidle and Barab, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 1962; 1917, **29**, 71). In this way a fairly concentrated sol was obtained, which remained stable for at least one year.

Zirconium oxide content was determined by drying the sol (5c.c.) at 110-20° and finally igniting it on a burner. The nitrate content was determined by the procedure suggested by Kolthoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 1454). The sol (5c.c.) was coagulated with sodium sulphate and washed till free of nitrate, as tested by brucine (B. D. H., "Organic Reagents for Analytical Uses", 1949, p. 29). To the filtrate and washings an excess of a standard solution of ferrous sulphate was added. The unconsumed ferrous sulphate was backtitrated against a standard solution of potassium dichromate, using diphenylamine as an indicator. Free zirconium was found to be absent. Purity of the sol is expressed as the ratio of ZrO_2 to NO_3^- , both being expressed in terms of g./litre. The relevant data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Sol.	ZrO ₂ . (a)	Conc. of NO ₃ ⁻ . (b)	Purity. (a/b)
G	30.5 g./litre	3.142 ² g./litre	10
H	25.6	2.067	12
I	21.6	1.034	21
L	22.2	1.736	13

Change in Conductance on Ageing.—The conductance of zirconium oxide sol was determined over a number of days. Doubly distilled water (sp. cond. = 2.0×10^{-6} mhos at 35°) was employed for dilution, its conductance being neglected. The dilutions were checked by analysis. The conductance of the sol was measured at 35°. Three sols were examined. Their behaviour being found similar, some of the results of one of them (sol L) are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Sol L.

No. of days.	Specific conductance $\times 10^4$			
	100%.	50%.	25%.	12.5%.
0	11.740	5.824	3.249	2.369
7	11.700	5.848	3.331	2.452
26	11.610	5.882	3.487	2.500
63	11.600	6.057	3.909	2.870
104	11.650	6.172	4.107	2.929

Change in Conductance on Dilution.—Three sols (G, H, and I) were diluted to different extents and changes in conductance on dilution were measured. The data regarding the specific and equivalent conductances in the case of sol I are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Sol I.

Conc. of ZrO ₂ sol.	Conc. of NO ₃ ⁻ in the micelles.	Conductance of the micelles.		Change in equiv. conduct. (λ).
		specific.	Equiv. (λ)	
21.60 g./litre	50.00 m.e./litre	9.649×10^{-4}	19.300	111.5%
19.44	45.00	8.638	19.230	111.2
17.28	40.00	7.661	18.900	109.4
15.12	35.00	6.407	18.310	106.0
12.96	30.00	5.370	17.900	103.6
10.80	25.00	4.316	17.270	100.0
8.64	20.00	3.469	17.350	100.5
6.48	15.00	2.660	17.730	102.7
4.32	10.00	1.928	19.280	111.6
2.16	5.00	1.370	27.390	158.6

DISCUSSION

Effect of Ageing.—It is observed that the specific conductance increases on ageing, the behaviour being more marked, the greater the dilution. On the other hand, in the case of original sol there is a tendency towards a decrease in specific conductance on ageing. Similar behaviour was noticed before (Jha and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 271; Parikh *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, 39, 711). Ageing brings into

play two opposing tendencies: (a) aggregation of micelles leading to the decrease in specific conductance and (b) desorption of the stabilising electrolyte which leads to the increase in specific conductance. The former tendency is prominent in the case of concentrated sols, whereas the latter comes into prominence as the sols are diluted.

Effect of Dilution.—Sols G, H, and I, which were of the order of increasing purity, were examined for the effect of dilution. In the first place, in all cases the specific conductance of the sol decreases on increasing the purity (data not given). Again, as noted previously, the conductance decreases on dilution and then increases, the effect becoming more marked as the purity is increased. To obtain the relation between conductance and dilution in the case of sols of different degrees of purity, the lowest value of the equivalent conductance in each case has been taken as 100% and the corresponding increase or decrease is plotted against the square root of the concentration (see Fig. 1). The detailed data of sol I are given in Table III. Hence zirconium oxide sols

FIG. 1

may also be classified as a colloidal electrolyte (Parikh *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

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